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**Magnifying Campus Nutrition: A Study Evaluating Dormitory Living,
Academic Demands, and CHED Policies on Legal Management
Students' Eating Habits at SSCR-Manila**

by:

Eloisa Mae Bruan (<https://orcid.org/0009-0003-8443-1464>) & Redge Sampior
(<https://orcid.org/0009-0008-9593-432X>)

Chapter I

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Nutrition is one of the most important things in a students' overall health, academic performance, and well-being. The World Health Organization said, *“Healthy students learn better and those with enough nutrition become more productive.”* Proper nutrition supports mental clarity, energy levels, concentration, and emotional stability, all of which are important for success in academics. However despite its importance, many college students find it difficult to maintain healthy eating habits because of many factors including the responsibilities of independent living in their dormitory, academic workload, limited financial capability, and restricted availability of healthy foods. The problem becomes more evident among Legal Management students at San Sebastian College-Recoletos Manila, whose academic

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and time pressures most of the time result in meal skipping, fast food dependence, or inadequate food budgeting.

The Commission on Higher Education (CHED) has proposed policies aimed at promoting student health and nutrition. The *CHED Memorandum Order No. 21, Series of 2000*, particularly *Section 10*, required that higher education institutions (HEIs) ensure the availability of safe, adequate, and healthful food within and around school premises. Additionally, the *CHED Memorandum Order No. 09, Series of 2013*, outlines the importance of Student Welfare and Development Programs, emphasizing that student services should support holistic development, which includes attention to nutrition and health.

This study aims to explore the eating habits of Legal Management students living in dormitories, identifying the environmental, academic, and economic factors that influence their food choices. And by integrating the research in those two existing CHED guidelines, this study also evaluates how well institutional policies are being reflected in the daily lives of students, and where improvements may be necessary to support healthier, more sustainable eating habits.

Review of Related Literature

This part presents a review of related literature regarding students who reside in a dormitory and how their culture, physical and social environment influence their eating habits. By understanding these influences, this study seeks to understand how academic pressure, time constraints, budget limitations, and living conditions

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contribute to their unhealthy eating habits. This study also seeks to provide evidence-based insights that may raise awareness among students and inform institutional recommendations aimed at supporting healthier food choices. Furthermore, it expounds on the struggle of the students in keeping a healthy lifestyle with various factors that cause a nutrient deficiency and that affects their physical health, academic performance, and overall well-being where they no longer maximize their productivity and body capability. Understanding these patterns is crucial to fostering a more health-conscious student community and aligning support services with their real needs.

College Students' Eating Patterns

In the study of Daour et al., (2022), university years are a critical transition stage for students, some move out from their homes and become independent adults which means they take full responsibility for their lifestyle including their eating habits, and through this, they might adopt undesirable eating and lifestyle behaviors.

Socioeconomic and Demographic Influences on Food Choices

According to a new Journal of Marketing study, "How Socioeconomic Status Shapes Food Preferences and Perceptions," by Bernardo Andretti et., (2025), Economic constraints limit access to healthy foods, as lower-income individuals often prioritize affordability and satiety (fillingness) over healthiness, making calorie-dense, less nutritious options more appealing.

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This supports the study of Lavelle et al., 2017; Perry et al., 2017 as per cited by Araque-Padilla and Montero-Simo (2025), which explains the ability to plan, select, prepare, and consume healthy foods is shaped by both socioeconomic and demographic factors. In disadvantaged communities, food literacy levels are often lower due to limited resources, restricted access to grocery stores, inadequate kitchen facilities, and time constraints related to income generation.

Psychological and Behavioral Aspects of Food Choices

The findings of Daour et al., (2022), showed a trend of poor eating habits, such as not meeting the recommended intake of fruits, vegetables, and water, as well as physical activity guidelines which linked to students facing academic-related stress, psychosocial stressors, emotional challenges and socioeconomic concerns.

Influence of Campus Environments on Food Habits

A few studies, by Dahl, et al (2024) has mentioned the abundance of energy-dense, nutrient-poor foods and sugary beverages on campus as well-documented. Limited healthy options and the high cost of fruits and vegetables discourage students from making healthier choices.

In the study of Cohen et al. (2021), they recognized that schools are an important setting to promote healthy behaviors because most of the students tend to spend their waking hours at school. They see that as an opportunity for the school to promote and establish healthier eating habits through access to nutritious foods, including breakfast and lunch. Many countries have nutrition standards for school

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meals, which can have important short- and long-term health implications for children, including promoting optimal growth and cognitive development and reducing the risk of food insecurity and obesity.

Meal Preparation and Food Insecurity in College Students

Meal preparations have been around for quite a long time and are undoubtedly one of the best solutions for food insecurity and poor eating habits. Miller et al., (2023), a study on college students with food insecurity found that meal preparation skills are crucial for improving dietary quality. However, time demands, limited financial resources, and lack of motivation may limit these skills. The study found that students with food insecurity had lower meal preparation skills and perceived ability to consume a healthy diet compared to those with food security. Barriers to healthy eating included convenience, time, and cost. Students suggested campus-provided support for meal preparation, including cooking classes, food pantry ideas, and grocery shopping incentives.

Financial Sustainability in School Nutrition Programs

The study of Slentz 2020, "The Value of Food: A Small Rural School Cafeteria Budget Case Study", is an important study that looks at how small rural schools can continue to have profitable nutrition programs. The study emphasizes that dedication to providing high-quality food, a committed workforce, and effective kitchen operations are characteristics of successful programs. It highlights how crucial it is to buy high-quality ingredients and make meals from scratch to stay within the National School Lunch Program's guidelines and prevent deficiencies.

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Cultural and Environmental Interventions

In the study of Jayasinghe, Byrne and Hills (2025), it was talked about that eating habits are shaped by changes in the natural environment, shifts in lifestyle, and more prominently, technology advancement. A noticeable paradigm shift has occurred, leaning toward predominantly unhealthy food choices in tandem with drastic transformations in global food systems and supply chains. For example, increasing national wealth and urbanization have driven higher consumption of animal products and processed foods while reducing the intake of healthier options like whole grains and legumes. This transition is further fueled by environmental factors that facilitate easy access to unhealthy foods, their affordability, and aggressive marketing strategies promoting them.

Statement of the Problem

It is commonly observed that undergraduate students residing in a dormitory show various challenges that crucially impact their eating habits. Legal Management Students' studying at San Sebastian College Recoletos - Manila who are living in dormitories often compromise their eating habits because of the inconvenience of choosing what affordable food has the right nourishment, limited time brought by the demands of academic life, and due to the repetitive choices in the menu. These could increase the chances of acquiring bad eating habits which may result in possible nutritional deficiencies and may further develop into health complications in the long term. This study aims to better understand the eating habits of the SSCR-Manila Legal Management Students' and explore if there is a potential

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improvement for a convenient solution to their unfavorable eating habits. The research aims to determine and assess the viability of providing recommendations for healthier and budget-friendly meals to support their dietary needs, and whether this can be of any help to sustain their healthy eating

Research Questions

1. What are the daily eating routines of students in terms of meal timing, frequency, and types of food consumed?
2. What key factors (e.g., financial constraints, dormitory rules, academic workload, peer influence, food accessibility) influence students' eating habits, and how do these factors shape their choices?
3. To what extent are students aware of SSCR-Manila and CHED nutritional guidelines, and how do these policies impact their access to nutritious meals?
4. What challenges do students face in maintaining balanced meals within dormitory settings, and what strategies do they employ to overcome these challenges?
5. How do dietary challenges and poor nutritional habits affect students' academic performance (e.g., focus, energy levels, attendance)?
6. What is the perceived relationship between diet, stress, and mental clarity among students, and how do specific foods influence these factors?

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7. How do students adjust their eating habits during periods of academic stress or busy schedules (e.g., exam periods)?
8. What personal strategies and small, sustainable changes do students adopt to maintain a healthy diet?
9. What improvements do students suggest for SSCR-Manila or CHED to better support their nutritional needs?

Theoretical Framework

Introduction

This paper explores the factors that influence the eating habits of Legal Management students studying at San Sebastian College Recoletos - Manila residing in a dormitory using these two theoretical approaches: Ecological Systems Theory (EST) and Health Belief Model (HBM). EST is a framework based on the idea that can explain how the environment that the students are living in impacts and shapes the development of their lives including their eating habits. The Health Belief Model is used to predict the likelihood of healthy eating habits among the Legal Management students. The next sections explain the background of the said theories and the rationale behind the decisions made for this theoretical framework.

Ecological Systems Theory

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The Ecological Systems Theory which was developed in 1979 by Urie Bronfenbrenner suggests that people encounter different environments throughout their life that may influence their behavior in various ways including eating habits. As stated by Reuter, Bridget, Forster & Brister (2019), young adults, particularly those in their early 20s, move from school to college where newfound independence may lead them to engage in unfavorable eating habits. These behaviors are prominent among those who live away from their family while those who still live with their parents engage in much healthier dietary intake. Their eating habits have changed negatively as a result of their loss of parental supervision and food preparation skills as students become adjusted to their new surroundings and resources.

Applying Ecological Systems Theory to determine the eating habits of the Legal Management students reveals multiple factors influencing their decisions. Their eating habits are greatly influenced by their physical surroundings, such as the availability of healthy food options, vending machines, and convenience stores. Peer groups and dorm culture are examples of social networks that frequently have a significant impact on encouraging or discouraging particular behaviors. External factors that influence their eating habits include institutional restrictions, such as meal plan structures, curfews in dorms, and access to cooking facilities. The Ecological Systems Theory is the best framework for thoroughly examining Legal Management students' eating habits since it emphasizes how linked these environmental elements are to each other.

Health Belief Model

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The Health Belief Model was created in the 1950s by social psychologists Irwin M. Rosenstock, Godfrey M. Hochbaum, S. Stephen Kegeles, and Howard Leventhal to explain how individuals see health threats and the likelihood that actions taken toward that goal will be achieved. According to a research conducted by Amore, Buchthal & Banna (2019), college students frequently eat fast food or fried foods and have poor eating habits, consuming fewer fruits and vegetables than the recommended five servings per day by the World Health Organization. Because of the abundance of low-nutrient, high-energy foods and the high-calorie atmosphere of dormitories, the college environment has been dubbed an "obesogenic environment", as it is closely linked to the influence on the conditions it occupies and the determination of individuals' choices that can promote the emergence of obesity. It is attractive and encouraging, in many ways, for the individual to adopt behaviors that are not aligned with practices that will benefit health as mentioned in the study of Swinburg, B Egger, Graza F (1999) and Tribole E, Resch E (2012) cited by Barbalho on "Factors of an Obesogenic Environment That Influence in Human Food Behavior" (2021). Applying the Health Belief Model to this study is helpful through which to examine the eating habits of Legal Management students residing in dormitories studying at SSCR-Manila.

Rationale

University life is often a time of transition and newfound independence. For many students, it's the first time they're living away from home, and with that comes the responsibility of managing their own lifestyle, including what they eat. At first, it

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may seem like a small adjustment such as picking up snacks on the go or grabbing fast food between classes but over time, these seemingly small choices can add up, leading to unhealthy eating habits. According to Daour, R. A. et al. (2022), this stage in a student's life can significantly impact their eating habits. The lack of structure, the pressure of academic responsibilities, and the temptation of easy, unhealthy food options may eventually result in long-term health problems.

To understand why students might fall into these habits, the study uses the Health Belief Model, for this model helps us look at the situation from a broader perspective, focusing on personal beliefs and environmental factors that influence students' choices. Students may not realize the risks of poor eating or might underestimate how serious the long-term effects could be. HBM considers these perceptions, as well as the benefits of healthier eating, such as improved energy, focus, and better academic performance. With these insights, the research aims to explore how schools can support students by providing healthier, more affordable food options on campus or making them aware of eating healthy through seminars. This would give students a better chance to make nutritious choices despite their busy schedules or limited budgets.

However, it doesn't stop with just understanding individual choices. The Ecological Systems Model expands the focus to the larger community and environment. When students transition from living at home to dorm life, they face new challenges in maintaining healthy eating habits. The environment around them whether it's the availability of healthy food options, irregular meal schedules, or peer

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influence shapes their decisions. These external factors are often out of the student's control but have a significant impact on their eating habits. The model suggests that the campus itself plays a crucial role in guiding students toward better eating behaviors. It's not just about what students choose but also about creating a campus environment where healthy choices are easier and more accessible.

The Ecological Systems Theory contextualizes student eating behavior across environments: microsystems (dorms), mesosystems (school-dorm interaction), and exosystems (institutional policies). The Health Belief Model, in parallel, explains why students—despite awareness—don't consistently act on health knowledge. Synthesizing these understands behavior not as isolated choice, but as socially and environmentally conditioned action constrained by perceived barriers.

In practice, these insights can lead to actionable changes. By understanding how external factors like the availability of healthy food options and peer influence affect students, it can propose interventions that adjust campus policies to provide more nutritious meals. The HBM offers a pathway to address barriers like time and cost by suggesting practical solutions, such as budget-friendly, healthy meal options or cooking workshops. This combined approach can help break down the obstacles preventing students from making healthier choices, ultimately improving their nutrition, well-being, and academic success.

Thus, with the help of these two models, the research not only identifies the causes of unhealthy eating but also lays out a clear path to better support students. By addressing both individual beliefs and environmental factors, it can create an

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environment that encourages healthy eating, fostering both better physical health and improved academic performance. The findings provide a roadmap for universities to create lasting, positive changes in their students' lives—helping them thrive not just in their studies, but in their overall well-being as well.

Conceptual Framework

The paper will be using the IPO Model for the study of Legal Management Students' Eating Habits Living in Dormitories Studying at SSCR-Manila: Implications of CHED Memorandum Order No. 21 Series 2000 and Memorandum Order No. 09 Series 2013 on Student Nutrition.

According to Management Consulted (2024), the IPO model is a tool for understanding systems, processes, and projects. It is used in a variety of industries and fields. The IPO model breaks a system down into three basic categories: inputs, processes, and outputs. The IPO model represents a system in three stages: input, process, and output.

Inputs are modeled as consumables and efforts that are introduced to a system at the beginning stage of the life cycle. Outputs are modeled as the result produced by the system. The process is modeled as the conversion of the inputs to the outputs. The IPO model is an easy-to-use, versatile framework used in various industries to define key process input variables, streamline operations, and aid in problem-solving. It helps identify bottlenecks, redundancies, and inefficiencies, enabling teams to allocate resources effectively. The model also aids in training and

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documentation, providing a visual representation of a business process, making it easier to convey information and train new employees. It also clarifies process steps and why, eliminating what doesn't produce a good outcome. It has found practical applications in general systems theory and design, improving quality and efficiency in various industries. Examples include manufacturing, online order processing, and software development. IPO diagrams can be used in social sciences, food and hospitality, economics, and finance planning, as they are foundational and applicable to various fields. (Experience Cloud 2023).

Visual Representation of IPO Model:

Fig 1. Conceptual Framework

IPO Model

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The main factors influencing the students' eating habits include the availability of food, the demands of school, and living in a dorm all have a big influence on how the student's eat.

The IPO model's structural alignment of inputs (dormitory life, time/budget restrictions), processes (coping mechanisms, food-related decision-making), and outputs (nutrition patterns, academic focus, and stress) demonstrates its usefulness. As students describe certain inputs (like dorm restrictions) and their behavioral responses (like missing meals), the findings from the interviews clearly translate onto each component.

Significance of the Study

Currently in the fast-paced life of an SSCR-Manila college student, daily meals often become an afterthought overshadowed from the morning rush, up to the evening lull, by the demands of school lectures, projects, homework, and exams. This leads to many students opting for quick and convenient, but sometimes unhealthy food choices. As students themselves, the researchers observed this common combination of factors such as busy schedules, limited financial resources, and inadequate access to healthy balanced food options around the campus has resulted in creating eating habits that may adversely affect students' long-term health and well-being.

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The importance of this research lies in its ambition to uncover the true main causes behind these eating behaviors. Instead of merely highlighting the problem itself, this study purposely seeks to identify and to understand why the SSCR-Manila Legal Management Students' who are living in a dormitory have poor eating behaviors such as missing their timely meals or choosing unhealthy meals, and distinguish the barriers that prevent them from making healthier food choices. If the researchers have learnt these challenges, then it is possible that the researchers aim would be successful by offering actionable solutions that can possibly improve students' diet and nutrition which ultimately enhance their overall college experience.

CHED Memorandum Order No. 21, Series of 2000 and CHED Memorandum Order No. 09, Series of 2013, which both stress the significance of student well-being and access to safe, healthful food as components of holistic education, are also evaluated through this research. Findings from this study will assess how well these national policies are implemented on a practical level within SSCR-Manila, and where policy alignment may be lacking.

By addressing the nutritional challenges faced by SSCR-Manila Legal Management students, this research could foster greater awareness of the importance of nutrition and encourage healthier eating habits. The research findings that will be collected by the researchers could serve as a very important piece for their output. A motivation for school administrators to consider policies or programs that support student wellness, such as affordable and accessible healthy food options or nutrition education initiatives. This isn't just about better diets, it's about

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creating an environment where students can succeed, both in their studies and in their personal lives.

Scope and Delimitations of the Study

The scope of our study is to understand the Impact of Several Factors on the Eating Habits of Legal Management Students' Living in a Dormitory studying at SSCR-Manila and explore how CHED Memorandum Order No. 21 Series 2000 and Memorandum Order No. 09 Series 2013 can be applied to improve nutrition among them.

The study is delimited only for the Legal Management Students' that live in a dormitory studying at San Sebastian College Recoletos - Manila. The main purpose of our study is to understand the Impact of Several Factors on the Eating Habits of Legal Management Students' Living in a Dormitory studying at SSCR-Manila. The study only focuses on providing recommendations for correcting current bad eating habits the students acquired and ensuring that students have access to nutritious meals and have healthy eating habits introducing healthy options and raise awareness with the consideration of the Legal Management students' in planning for eating out, such as the variables of budget constraints, beliefs, enjoyment in eating out and meal planning. The study excludes providing an investment plan into considering selling out the healthy products that the researchers introduced. The operational cost is also excluded in the study because the researchers only limit the study to introduce a healthy meal option and not to sell the said products. This concludes that the only intention of the researchers team is to understand the Impact

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of Several Factors on Eating Habits of the Legal Management Students' Residing in Dormitories studying at SSCR-Manila, to be specific, the researchers intentions are to track the budget, the eating habits of the students, and how can the school properly utilize a healthy culture and environment in introducing a better meal options that would help the students to create a society a better and healthier environment that would greatly benefit both the students and their academic performance in building a healthier body.

As a qualitative study, the emphasis is on thematic understanding rather than numerical generalization. A misleading perception of representativeness that the study's design does not strive for may be produced if the researchers will use percentages. Instead, frequency counts and saturation cues guide interpretation.

Definition of Terms

- **Ecological Systems Theory**

A theory that emphasizes the interconnectedness of individuals and their environments, explaining how various environmental systems (e.g., family, peers, institutions) influence behavior, including eating habits.

- **Health Belief Model**

A model that predicts health behaviors based on individuals' perceptions of health threats, benefits of taking action, barriers to action, and self-efficacy in

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making changes.

- **Obesogenic Environment**

An environment that promotes weight gain and unhealthy eating habits due to the easy availability of energy-dense, nutrient-poor foods and limited opportunities for physical activity.

- **Nutritional Deficiencies**

A lack of essential vitamins, minerals, and other nutrients required for optimal health and bodily functions.

- **Descriptive Research**

A research approach that focuses on describing the characteristics of a phenomenon or population, often using surveys and interviews to gather data.

- **Purposive Sampling**

It is a research method where participants are chosen intentionally based on specific characteristics or knowledge they possess that are relevant to the research question.

- **Convenience Foods**

Processed or prepared foods that are quick and easy to consume but often

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high in calories, unhealthy fats, sugar, and sodium.

- **Health Promotion**

The process of enabling people to increase control over their well-being to improve outcomes.

- **Dietary Habits**

The usual pattern of food choices and consumption.

- **Campus Cafeteria**

A dining facility located on a college or university campus, typically providing meals to students, faculty, and staff.

- **Undergraduate Students**

Students pursuing a bachelor's degree at a college or university.

- **Dormitories**

Residential buildings on a college campus where students live.

- **SSCR-Manila**

San Sebastian College - Recoletos, Manila, the specific institution where the research is being conducted.

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- **Intervention**

A program or strategy designed to change behavior or improve health outcomes.

- **Public Health Initiatives**

Organized efforts to improve the health of a population.

- **Long-Term Health Consequences**

The negative health outcomes that can develop over time due to unhealthy lifestyle choices, such as poor diet.

- **Socioeconomic Factors**

Economic and social conditions that influence individuals' lives, such as income, education, and occupation.

- **Budget Constraints**

Limitations on spending due to financial resources.

- **Primary Data**

Original information collected directly from a source.

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- **I-P-O Model**

Input-Process-Output model, a framework for understanding the flow of activities in a system.

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Chapter II

METHODOLOGY

This chapter discusses the research methods that will be used in the study, namely the overall research design of the paper as well the methods of gathering the data, sampling techniques, research instruments, and statistical treatment of the data.

Research Design

In order to describe the current state of the study using primary data, the researchers will employ descriptive research as their research design. According to Singh (2023), descriptive research is a methodological approach focused on describing the characteristics of a subject or phenomenon, as it serves as the foundation for scientific inquiry. It provides a detailed account of a subject, aiding in understanding, categorizing, and interpreting it. This approach is widely used across various fields. Its objective is primarily to create a system that observes and documents all variables and conditions that influence the phenomenon.

As stated by Maione (2023), primary data is original information collected for the first time, primary data collection aims to obtain the most accurate, latest information that can be used to develop products and improve services or processes. This system of gathering data directly from sources such as people and actual occasions.

Using primary data, the research will be able to directly examine and address the eating habits and challenges faced by Legal Management students at

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SSCR-Manila. This will not only provide accurate and relevant information but will also guide the development of targeted solutions to improve their eating habits. Whether through surveys, interviews, or even experimental trials, primary data collection is essential to understand the problem in-depth and offer evidence-based recommendations for healthier and more convenient food options on campus.

Research Locale

The research will be conducted at San Sebastian College Recoletos-Manila, a private Catholic Christian co-curricular basic and higher education institution run by the Order of Augustinian Recollects in Manila, Metro Manila, Philippines (SSCR-Manila Website).

The institution houses the Legal Management program under its College of Arts and Sciences and this study will specifically focus on Legal Management as there are students that came from distant places which prompts them to live in dormitories for easier access to the school. These living arrangements, combined with the demands of what a Legal Management student is, explores the environmental, academic, and economic factors affecting their eating habits. The research will assess how these conditions align with or challenge CHED's policies on student nutrition and welfare or help develop recommendations for healthier meal options for a better academic life.

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Sampling Design

This study will use purposive sampling, a non-probability sampling technique where participants are deliberately selected based on specific characteristics relevant to the research objectives. According to Memon et al. (2025), purposive sampling involves the intentional selection of individuals who possess particular attributes that align closely with the study's aims, enabling researchers to gather in-depth and relevant data.

For this study, the researchers intentionally select students enrolled in the Legal Management program at SSCR-Manila who reside in dormitories. They are chosen to ensure that the participants have direct experience with the factors under investigation, specifically, how dormitory living conditions influence their eating habits in relation to academic pressures and institutional policies on student nutrition.

Purposive sampling allows for the collection of clear and detailed information that is useful to the research questions. This method enables a deeper understanding of the challenges and behaviors of Legal Management students living in dormitories, providing valuable insights into their eating habits and the potential impact of educational policies.

Instrumentation

The researchers will use a survey questionnaire to gather data. Survey questionnaires will be administered by the researchers which include open-ended questions to allow for more detailed responses that are specifically designed to

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gather specific information related to the research objectives. The researchers will send out the survey questionnaires which are conducted online. Applying qualitatively, the researchers will have direct interaction with the participants, followed by a fixed set of questions. To apply the following instruments, researchers will attach a consent letter and inform the participants about the purpose of the study and how the data will be used.

The researchers also ensure that the instruments being used must accurately measure what they intend to measure, to create questions that are unbiased and relevant, it must be clear and understandable for the participants to answer specifically. And the researchers have conducted a pilot test with two dormitory-residing Legal Management students. Although the sample size is limited, this aligns with the approach suitable for qualitative instruments. The objective was not to generalize, but to discern ambiguities and modify the instrument to align with the actual experiences of the target population.

While only nine people make up this study's sample size, it is in line with qualitative research methods, especially when working with a small, homogeneous group. Understanding the lived experiences and viewpoints of a particular group in great detail is the aim of qualitative research, not statistical generalization. Thematic saturation in qualitative interviews can frequently be attained with as little as nine to twelve interviews, particularly when the study's scope is limited and participants have comparable backgrounds, as according to Hennink, Kaiser, and Marconi (2022). Since all participants in this study are SSCR-Manila dormitory-residing Legal

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Management students, the sample is reasonably homogeneous and perfect for in-depth analysis. As a result, using nine respondents is both methodologically right and adequate to produce deep, trustworthy qualitative insights.

Instrument Validation

Although external expert validation is common in traditional research, this study opted for a more adaptive validation process. According to Roth, 2024; SciencePo, 2024, in their research it shows that external experts are not always the best source for judging questionnaire quality due to a potential unlinkness from lived realities and participant contexts. Experts may prioritize technical correctness over practical usability, which can result in instruments that do not align with participant experience.

Furthermore, Ríos et al. (2021) argue that content validity must include user-centered criteria, especially in qualitative contexts, where insights often appear inductively. Therefore, instead of solely relying on external experts, the researchers piloted the instrument with two target respondents. Feedback from the pilot led to revisions in question phrasing and structure to enhance clarity and eliminate biases.

This paper also applied the frameworks of Beghetto et al. (2024) and Capinding (2024), which recommend modern, LLM-informed validation strategies for greater practicality, inclusivity, and reduced structural bias in social science tools.

Data Gathering Procedure

A letter of request was prepared by the researchers to conduct the study at

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San Sebastian College-Recoletos Manila. The researchers constructed a survey questionnaire checklist, which was validated by the professor of the subject. The survey questionnaires were then distributed. Data gathering was conducted within the premises of San Sebastian College-Recoletos Manila, focusing exclusively on Legal Management students residing in dormitories. The survey questionnaires were distributed both in person and via digital platforms (Google Forms) to maximize accessibility for dormitory students. Prior to distribution, a consent letter was provided to all participants, ensuring that they were aware of the study's purpose, the confidentiality of their responses, and their voluntary participation. Data collection was conducted for eleven days, during which the researchers ensured that responses were gathered from all selected participants. Once collected, the responses were sorted, coded, and analyzed in accordance with the study's theoretical and conceptual frameworks.

Data Analysis

This chapter provides a wide variety of examples of data analysis techniques and questionnaires used for studying students' eating habits and the demand for new healthy food options.

Qualitative data from interviews and open-ended questions in surveys will be analyzed using thematic analysis. These techniques will allow for the identification and interpretation of patterns, themes, and insights related to cultural and environmental factors that influence students' eating habits. Thematic Analysis is a method for identifying, analyzing, and reporting patterns (themes) within data”

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according to Sovacool, Iskandarova, Hall (2023). This technique will be used to derive meaning from students' responses, interviews, and open-ended survey questions. After transcribing interviews and collecting open-ended responses, the data will be reviewed multiple times and organized into key themes, such as cultural influences on food choices (traditional diets, family preferences, school policies), perceptions of the school cafeteria (food quality, accessibility), personal barriers to eating healthier (time, cost, convenience, and the perceived impact of diet on academic performance such as focus, energy, cognitive ability). The process of analyzing qualitative data involves several key steps: first, familiarization occurs through immersion in the data by reading transcripts multiple times; then, initial coding is performed by identifying significant portions of text, such as sentences or phrases, that relate to the research question. These codes are grouped into broader themes during the theme identification phase, and finally, the reviewing of themes ensures that the identified themes accurately reflect the data, refining and defining them as necessary for clarity and consistency.

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Chapter III

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1

Factors Identified in Influencing the Legal Management Dormitory Students Eating Habits

Theme	Description	Example Quote	Frequency
Academic Workload	School tasks and responsibilities the Legal Management students need to comply with.	"There are times when I can't cook food because it's time-consuming and I have a lot of schoolwork and reading to do."	6/9
Food Accessibility	Legal Management Students' access to meals they are consuming daily.	"The location of my dorm is surrounded by different fast food restaurants. I depend on these establishments..."	5/9

Note. Themes emerged from semi-structured interviews with 9 students. Frequency reflects the number of participants mentioning the theme.

Explanation of Results

Two primary themes emerged from student interviews. Food Accessibility was frequently cited (5 out of 9 participants), with students talking about what is only available around their area of dormitory. Academic Workload has almost the same frequency (4 out of 9 participants), mentioning busy schedules due to the amount of school tasks they need to do. Representative quotes illustrate these themes.

Table 2

Challenges faced in Maintaining Balanced Meals in a Dormitory by the Legal Management Dormitory Students

Theme	Description	Example Quote	Frequency
Time Constraints	Limited time for meal preparation due to academic workload and busy schedules.	"I don't have time to cook, so I rely on fast food, and it affects my energy levels during the day."	4/9
Budget	Financial constraints impacting meal choices, leading to prioritizing cost over quality.	"The only foods that I can easily spend my money on are eggs and simple vegetables/fruits."	5/9
Cultural / Dietary Preferences	Personal food preferences are influenced by culture or dietary habits.	"I don't like to stock much food at home so I wouldn't be tempted. But I do have the healthy essentials."	2/9
Lack of Cooking Facilities	Dormitory rules and lack of facilities for cooking lead to reliance on less healthy food options.	"It's not allowed to cook inside, so I have to rely on fast food, which isn't always the healthiest."	3/9

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Note. Themes emerged from semi-structured interviews with 9 students. Frequency reflects the number of participants mentioning the theme.

Explanation of Results

Four primary themes emerged from student interviews. Budget was frequently cited (5 out of 9 participants), with students talking about their limited financial capability in buying healthy foods. Time Constraints come second (4 out of 9 participants), mentioning busy schedules as well resulting in the lack of time for meal preparation. Lack of Cooking Facilities come third (3 out of 9 participants), illustrating restrictions leading them to rely on less healthy food options. Lastly, Cultural / Dietary Preferences (2 out of 9 participants), which talks about student’s personal food preferences as influenced by culture or dietary habits. Representative quotes illustrate these themes.

Table 3

Impact of the Challenges in their Academic Performance

Theme	Description	Example Quote	Frequency
Health-related Issues	The impact of unhealthy eating or skipping meals on energy, focus, and physical health.	"Skipping meals because I didn't have enough time to prepare a meal for myself made me feel sleepy and unfocused.	4/9

Note. The theme emerged from semi-structured interviews with 9 students. Frequency reflects the number of participants mentioning the theme.

Explanation of Results

One primary theme emerged from student interviews. Health-related Issues is the only one cited for this table (4 out of 9 participants), which is the impact of unhealthy eating or skipping meals. The representative quote illustrates the theme.

Table 4

Legal Management Students Personal Strategies or Resources to Maintain a Healthy Diet

Theme	Description	Example Quote	Frequency
Peer Influence	Influence from peers or support from friends in meal choices and strategies for healthy eating.	"I try as much as possible to balance my consumption with fast food restaurants. I opt to eat much healthier foods by budgeting."	1/9

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Self-discipline Personal effort in maintaining "Drinking more water helps a lot. I try to 6/9
healthy eating habits through avoid junk food and focus on better eating
planning, hydration, and meal habits."
prep.

Note. Themes emerged from semi-structured interviews with 9 students. Frequency reflects the number of participants mentioning the theme.

Explanation of Results

Two primary themes emerged from student interviews. Self-discipline was frequently cited (6 out of 9 participants), with students personal effort in maintaining healthy eating habits. Peer Influence is the second (1 out of 9 participants), with one student mentioning trying to as much as possible balance fast food consumption. Representative quotes illustrate these themes.

Discussion

The findings of this study from the gathered responses reflect multiple themes that impact the eating habits of Legal Management Students at SSCR Manila living in a dormitory, primarily influenced by their academic environment, time constraints, and socioeconomic limitations. These align with the Ecological Systems Theory and the Health Belief Model, and support recent literature on college eating habits as will be discussed further below.

Ecological Systems Theory was used to understand how the students' social and physical environments such as their living conditions, campus and within its vicinity food availability, and budget shape their eating habits. As the respondents stated, they would choose fast food or skip meals not out of preference, but because healthier options are too expensive or nowhere to be found near campus. This theory

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helped frame these choices as the result of environmental influences, rather than simply personal decisions.

Meanwhile, the Health Belief Model was used to analyze how students perceive the risks and consequences of their eating habits. Though many students are aware of the negative effects of having poor nutrition like low energy levels or decreased academic performance, they often perceive barriers (time constraints, lack of access to affordable food) that prevent them from making healthier choices. This model highlights the many influences and barriers on student eating habits.

Applying these two theories will help to better understand the reason for the students' eating habits as connected with well-established behavioral and environmental frameworks. It also helps to interpret the data more deeply and supports the conclusion that individual perceptions and environmental limitations must be addressed to promote healthier eating habits among the students.

1. Time

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The Legal Management Students who responded have mentioned skipping meals or opting for unhealthy meal options due to tight schedules and academic workload (See Frame: Time, Time Constraints and Academic Workload). Some students said *"Skipping meals because I didn't have enough time to prepare a meal for myself and also I don't have time to cook, so I rely on fast food, and it affects my energy levels during the day."* This reflects what Reuter et al. (2019) described emphasizing the effect of independence and university life transitions on eating habits. And the findings by South Australia's Breakfast Report (2024) which state that academic responsibilities directly affect eating habits. A student noted that *"Academic workload affects my eating choices because when I'm busy with my assignments or studying I don't have time to go out or eat outside, as a result of that I eat unhealthy food like fast foods sometimes grab food."* This shows that there are students who often compromise their healthy eating to meet deadlines.

This also shows what *CHED Memorandum Order No. 09 Series 2013*, particularly *Section 10.1* indicates about Student Welfare Services as essential for promoting students overall well-being and overall supports holistic student development. And *Section 26*, which highlights the institution's responsibility to ensure the availability of adequate, safe, and healthful food options in accordance with national food safety standards. When students' nutrition suffers due to the school demands, their mental focus and physical health decline, which is contrary to CHED's aim for well-rounded student welfare programs.

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According to Rural Health Information Hub (2025), the Health Belief Model can help explain why students continue to engage in unhealthy eating behaviors despite being aware of the consequences. In some of the responses, students likely recognize their susceptibility to negative health outcomes (fatigue or poor academic performance) and understand the severity of these effects on their daily university life. However, their decisions are often shaped by the perceived barriers such as time constraints, lack of access to nutritious food, or inability to cook which outweigh the perceived benefits of eating healthily. Even when students know that maintaining a nutritious diet could improve energy levels and academic focus, the challenge of balancing a demanding academic workload leads them to compromise on their eating habits. This imbalance between awareness and action illustrates how powerful perceived barriers can be. And it also goes to show that without institutional support or interventions that increase students' self-efficacy, these unhealthy habits are likely to persist.

2. Food and Budget

The Legal Management Students shared that the lack of budget-friendly food options near campus led them to eat fast food or food that is convenient given their situation living in a dormitory. (See Frame: Budget Constraints, Food Preferences and Meal Location), a student mentioned that *"I try as much as possible to balance my consumption with fast food restaurants. I opt to eat much healthier foods by budgeting since healthier options usually cost more."* This explains that students will

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tend to choose or even compromise the quality of their food over the quantity of its price because quality or healthier options are likely to cost more in their premises.

This correlates with the theory of Ecological Systems Theory as it explains that students' eating habits are influenced by their social and physical environments. In this study, Legal Management students shared that their food choices are not only influenced by what good will it do to them but also because of budget constraints and the physical availability of food options around them. This highlights that students' eating decisions are not always based on health, but affordability.

CHED Memorandum Order No. 21 Series 2000, particularly *Section 10* ensures adequate, safe, and healthful food within the campus and immediate vicinity. As shown by the results collected, there is the need for better accessibility of affordable healthy meals on or near campus.

3. Environment

The responses from Legal Management students highlight the significant impact of their living environment on their eating habits (See Frame: Academic Workload, Meal Location). Specifically, factors like dormitory location, accessibility to food, and the ability to prepare meals are crucial in shaping students' food choices. The students indicated that their eating decisions are influenced not just by the availability of food but by the convenience and proximity of food sources. One student stated, "*I really prefer home-cooked meals since I know how to cook and there is no dorm restriction with regard to cooking, but there are times when I can't cook food because it's*

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time-consuming and I have a lot of schoolwork and reading to do." This reflects the tension between students' desire for healthier, homemade food and the constraints imposed by a demanding academic schedule.

The Ecological Systems Theory can be applied here, as students' meal choices are influenced not only by their academic and social environments but also by the physical environment (availability of cooking facilities and food sources near their dorms). One student noted, *"The location of my dorm is surrounded by different fast food restaurants. I depend on these establishments."* This is consistent with Amore et al. (2019) concept of "obesogenic environments," where the easy accessibility of high-calorie, convenience foods contributes to unhealthy eating behaviors. In contrast, students who live in areas with limited access to food outlets or in dormitories with poor kitchen facilities often rely on convenience foods or struggle to find affordable and nutritious options. One respondent mentioned, *"Cause that's all around here that have affordable prices and available,"* illustrating how the proximity to fast food outlets shapes their eating habits.

Additionally, the challenge of food accessibility was further compounded for students with limited cooking facilities, especially for those in higher floors or with restricted access to transportation. One student commented, *"I don't like to stock much food at home so I wouldn't be tempted. But I do have the healthy essentials. My apartment is on the sixth floor, through stairs only, so that made my access limited."* This illustrates how environmental factors such as the physical layout of the

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living space and the convenience of grocery shopping influence students' eating habits.

Both *CHED Memorandum* does not specify particular subsections directly addressing the physical environment's impact on student nutrition. However, overall the memorandums cannot emphasize enough like in *Section 10.1 of CHED Memorandum Order No. 09 Series 2013* the importance of student welfare services that promote the well-being of the students, which can encompass the physical environment in a broader sense. While there may not be explicit subsections, this aligns with what CHED is aiming for holistic student development.

4. Stress

Looking at the code frame, findings show that Legal Management Students experience stress eating, particularly if under academic stress (See Frame: Diet and Mental Health and Stress Eating). Some students claim that they do stress eating and some don't and some have acknowledged they do but fixed their destructive habits. According to the study by Amore, Buchthal & Banna (2019), both sources link high stress levels in university students with a tendency to consume fast or high-calorie comfort foods. And according to the Health Belief Model, these behaviors came from low perceived susceptibility to long-term health issues despite high perceived barriers like cost and convenience.

Applying the *CHED Memorandum Order No. 09 Series 2013* specifically *Section 27.1* which mandates that higher education institutions provide primary

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health care services including mental health support administered by licensed medical, dental, and allied professionals., *Section 27.3* which calls for adequate, functional health facilities that can cater to students needs and *Section 27.4* which emphasizes the maintenance of updated health and disability records, underscoring the importance of monitoring and addressing student wellness holistically is helpful on promoting well mental health among students, as stress-induced eating signals a gap in both stress management and wellness promotion in academic settings. The World Health Organization links nutritional status to mental clarity and academic success. According to WHO, micronutrient deficiencies can lead to reductions in energy levels, mental clarity, and overall capacity, which in turn can result in decreased educational outcomes. These statements proved the importance of having proper nutrition in supporting cognitive function and academic success. Therefore, improving access to nutritious meals and spreading awareness can help boost student productivity.

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Chapter IV

RESEARCH IMPLICATIONS

Summary of Significant Findings

The responses from Legal Management students living in dormitories studying at SSCR-Manila revealed their current eating habits influenced by academic workload, budget constraints, and food accessibility. Most students responded to eating only once or twice a day, often skipping breakfast and relying on instant or fast food due to time constraints and their academic demands. Many acknowledged that stress and lack of motivation further discouraged healthy eating, and several shared that they eat whatever is quick or convenient especially during exam days. Tight budgets also led them to buy cheap but unhealthy options. While some students attempted budgeting or meal prepping, most lacked the time, space, or energy to do so consistently. Additionally, a majority were unaware of CHED's policies on student nutrition, and some had offered for the school to provide affordable and healthy food options moving forward and conduct seminars for students' awareness.

Conclusion

This study confirms that the eating habits of SSCR-Manila Legal Management students residing in a dormitory are significantly shaped by external constraints like academic pressure, limited time, budget constraints, and the surrounding food environment. These students recognize the effects of poor nutrition on their academic performance and energy levels but often feel powerless to make

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healthier choices given their conditions. The gap between policy and practice is evident that although CHED promotes access to safe and healthful food, implementation at the institutional level appears minimal. This research has shown us that solutions must begin with listening to student voices and understanding the systems that shape their everyday choices. As supported by findings from the UNESCO report Ready to Learn and Thrive: School Health and Nutrition Around the World (2023), *“Healthy students learn better, and those with enough nutrition become more productive”*.

Recommendations

The findings of this study reveal a clear need for institutional efforts to address the challenges faced by Legal Management dormitory students. Several respondents specifically recommended improvements in the quality, variety, and affordability of meals offered within the SSCR-Manila campus. One student said, *“To provide more healthy meals and delicious options within SSCR-Manila,”* suggesting that the current food offerings are insufficiently nutritious or appealing. Another one stated, *“Offer better and affordable meals for students,”* emphasizing the need for accessible options that strike a balance between nutritional value and cost. A similar concern was also said in the suggestion to *“give students a budget-friendly meal but healthy too. I noticed that most ‘affordable’ foods are not healthy such as fast foods, etc.”* These responses reflect a common concern that while inexpensive meals may be available, they are often unhealthy and limited in variety.

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These student recommendations align with the goals outlined in CHED Memorandum Order No. 21, Series of 2000, and CMO No. 09, Series of 2013, which mandate higher education institutions (HEIs) to support student health and welfare through access to safe, adequate, and healthful food. These findings point to a gap between policy and practice that must be addressed at the institutional level. Implementing clearer nutritional guidelines within campus food service contracts and expanding canteen options to include affordable, nutrient-dense meals would represent a meaningful step toward policy compliance and student wellness.

Moreover, considering the limitations of this study which focus on a single academic program that is the Legal Management, a small purposive sample of nine participants, and reliance on self-reported qualitative data-future research is encouraged to expand both in scope and methodology. Comparative studies across multiple academic programs and disciplines would allow for cross-sectional analysis of student eating habits. Additionally, integrating quantitative methods (dietary intake tracking, BMI assessment, or policy compliance metrics) could yield measurable outcomes and support evidence-based policymaking.

Future researchers may also consider designing intervention-based studies to test the effectiveness of proposed changes, such as Meal subsidy programs for dormitory students, peer-led cooking or budgeting workshops, nutrition awareness campaigns integrating CHED guidelines and feedback mechanisms like periodic cafeteria satisfaction surveys.

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All in all, this study serves as a call to action. Students should not have to choose between affordability and health in their daily meals. When schools proactively support both the mind and body, real change begins. A student-centered food environment is not only an academic support but a fundamental aspect of institutional care.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX A: INSTRUMENT AND CONSENT LETTER

Describe your typical daily eating routine in detail: *

1. *Meal timing:* (e.g., "I eat lunch at 12:00 PM, dinner at 7:00 PM...")
2. *Frequency:* How many meals/snacks do you typically consume daily?
3. *Types of food:* What do you usually eat? (e.g., "Fast food, home-cooked meals, snacks").

Long answer text
.....

What factors most significantly influence your current eating habits? (e.g., *financial constraints, dormitory rules, academic workload, peer influence, food accessibility*). How come? *

- Financial constraints
- Academic workload
- Food accessibility
- Peer influence
- Dormitory rules
- Other...

FOLLOW-UP: Why do these factors affect your choices? *

Long answer text
.....

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How familiar are you with SSCR-Manila or CHED guidelines on student welfare/nutrition? (e.g. CHED MO 21 s. 2000 (student welfare), MO 09 s. 2013 (dining facilities)). *

Not Aware 1 2 3 Very Aware

FOLLOW-UP: If aware, how do these policies affect your access to nutritious meals? *

Long answer text

What challenges do you face in maintaining balanced meals in a dormitory? *

- Budget
- Time
- Lack of cooking facilities
- Limited healthy options near campus
- Cultural/Dietary Preferences
- Other..

FOLLOW-UP: How do you navigate these challenges? *

Long answer text

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How do these challenges affect your academic performance? *

1. *Focus during exams*
2. *Energy levels*
3. *Attendance*

Long answer text
.....

FOLLOW-UP: Describe a specific instance where these issues impacted your studies. *

Long answer text
.....

How do you perceive the relationship between your diet and stress/mental clarity? *

Long answer text
.....

Do certain foods make you feel more anxious or fatigued? *

- Yes
- No
- Maybe

Do you think improving your diet will help you manage stress better? *

- Yes
- No
- Maybe

Describe a time when poor nutrition (e.g., *skipping meals, relying on junk food*) affected your academic performance. *

Long answer text

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During busy periods (e.g., exams), how do you adjust your eating habits? *

1. Meal preparation
2. Ordering delivery
3. Skipping meals
4. Stress eating

Long answer text
.....

What personal strategies or resources help you maintain a healthy diet? *

- Peer support
- University programs
- Online content (e.g. vlogs)
- Self-discipline
- Other...

What small, sustainable changes have improved your well-being? (e.g. *Drinking more water, reducing junk food, meal timing*). *

Long answer text
.....

How do you think SSCR-Manila or CHED could better support students' nutritional needs? *

Long answer text
.....

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By selecting "I Agree" below, you acknowledge that you have read and understood the information provided to you by the researchers and consent to participate in this study. *

I Agree

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Alcantara, Rodel Christian

Commercial Space 6 G/F, Crown Tower, 839 Tolentino St, Sampaloc
Manila City, Philippines, 1008

Subject: Request for Participation in Research Study

Dear Mr. Alcantara,

I hope this letter finds you well. My name is Redge Sampior, and I am an Undergraduate Student Researcher at San Sebastian College - Recoletos in Manila. I am conducting a research study titled "Legal Management Students' Eating Habits Living in Dormitories Studying at SSCR-Manila: Implications of RA 10862 Section 2 on Student Nutrition" to offer meaningful recommendations that align with the National Policies to improve the students eating habits residing in dormitories.

Your participation in this study is entirely voluntary, and you may withdraw at any time without any consequences or penalties. Should you choose to participate, your responses will be used solely for research purposes and will remain strictly confidential.

Research Details:

- **Project Title:** Legal Management Students' Eating Habits Living in Dormitories Studying at SSCR-Manila: Implications of RA 10862 Section 2 on Student Nutrition
- **Researchers:** Bruan, Eloisa Mae P., Sampior, Redge Jefferson A.
- **Purpose of Research:** To assess if there is an existing problem on the eating habits of the Legal Management Students residing in dormitories.

Voluntary Participation:

Participation in this research is completely voluntary. You may decline to answer any question or withdraw from the study at any point without any consequences.

Risks and Benefits:

- **Potential Risks:** There is a possible discomfort/anxiety on the part of sharing information about the students eating habits. And so, the respondents might give false information because of their insecurity.
- **Expected Benefits:** Gaining knowledge on the information they provide and by these, the researchers will be able to assess useful data that contribute to the research paper. And they will be given a monetary compensation of 100.00 for complying with the interview.

Confidentiality:

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Area of Business Administration

All information you provide will remain confidential and will be used only for research purposes. Your identity will not be disclosed in any reports or publications. Data will be securely stored and accessible only to authorized researchers.

Withdrawal from the Study:

If at any time you decide to withdraw from the study, your data will be excluded from the final analysis and permanently deleted if withdrawal occurs before data collection is complete.

Contact Information:

If you have any questions or concerns about this study, please feel free to contact:

- **Researcher:** Bruan, Eloisa Mae P., emp.bruan@sscrmnl.edu.ph, 09566611363 | Sampior, Redge Jefferson A., rja.sampior@sscrmnl.edu.ph, 09763768317
- **Research Adviser:** Mr. Dexter P. Bano Jr., dexter.banojr@sscrmnl.edu.ph, +639472650908

Consent Statement:

By signing below, you acknowledge that you have read and understood the details of the study. You voluntarily agree to participate and understand that you may withdraw at any time.

Participant's Name: _____

Signature: _____

Date: _____

Thank you for your time and consideration. Your participation is greatly appreciated.

Sincerely,

Sampior, Redge Jefferson A.
San Sebastian College - Recoletos, Manila
rja.sampior@sscrmnl.edu.ph | 09763768317

Noted by,

Mr. Dexter P. Bano Jr. (Research Lecturer)
San Sebastian College - Recoletos, Manila
+639472650908 | dexter.banojr@sscrmnl.edu.ph

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APPENDIX B: SUMMARY OF PILOT RESPONSES

Daily Eating Patterns

Describe your typical daily eating routine in detail:

1. Meal timing
2. Frequency
3. Types of food

2 responses

1. 12:00 nn - lunch
2. 3x a day
3. Fast food

1

What factors most significantly influence your current eating habits? (e.g., financial constraints, dormitory rules, academic workload, peer influence, food accessibility). How come?

2 responses

Food accessibility since there's so many fastfood or restaurant around my area

Workload

Policy and Institutional Context

Are you aware of any SSCR-Manila or CHED guidelines (e.g., CHED MO 21 s. 2000 or MO 09 s. 2013) related to student welfare or nutrition? If yes, how do you think these policies affect your access to nutritious meals or dining facilities?

2 responses

No

Challenges and Barriers

What challenges do you face in maintaining regular, balanced meals while living in a dormitory? (e.g., budget, time, lack of cooking facilities, limited healthy options near campus)

2 responses

Lack of cooking facilities in my dorm

Lack of cooking facilities and limited healthy options near campus

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How do these challenges impact your academic performance (e.g., focus during exams, energy levels)?

2 responses

Tiring but need to review

N/a

Stress, Nutrition, and Academic Performance

How do you perceive the relationship between your diet and your ability to manage stress or maintain mental clarity as a Legal Management student?

2 responses

As a Legal Management student, I've come to realize that my diet has a significant impact on how well I manage stress and maintain mental clarity. I've noticed that when I eat poorly—like indulging in too much caffeine or sugary snacks—I tend to feel more anxious, fatigued, and have a harder time focusing on my studies. These dips in energy and mood definitely make it more challenging to stay on top of assignments or perform well during exams.

On the other hand, when I make an effort to eat balanced meals with plenty of whole foods—like fruits, vegetables, lean proteins, and healthy fats—I feel more energized and able to concentrate better. I've noticed that my stress levels are more manageable when I'm properly fueled, and I can think more clearly during long study sessions. Staying hydrated also plays a big role, as dehydration tends to leave me feeling sluggish and foggy.

n/a

Describe a time when poor nutrition (e.g., skipping meals, relying on junk food) affected your academic performance.

2 responses

I had UTI and sore throat during my midterm exam week

skipping meals

Strategies for Healthy Eating

During busy periods (e.g., exams), how do you adjust your eating habits? What compromises do you make, and why?

2 responses

During my busy periods, I order food through online app.

i dont compromise, i usually do stress eating during busy periods

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What personal strategies or resources (e.g., university programs, peer support) help you maintain or improve your diet?

2 responses

Peer support and Vlogs about healthy lifestyle

n/a

Sustainability and Policy Suggestions

What small, sustainable changes have you made to your diet that improved your well-being?

2 responses

I've made it a habit to drink water regularly, not just when I'm thirsty. I've found that staying hydrated helps me stay focused and clear-headed, which is essential for long study sessions. I also avoided junk foods and soft drinks.

calorie deficit

How could SSCR-Manila or CHED better support students' nutritional needs based on your experiences?

2 responses

Both SSCR-Manila and CHED could organize workshops, seminars, or online campaigns that focus on the importance of nutrition for mental clarity and stress management. By educating students about how food impacts their academic performance and stress levels, they could empower students to make healthier food choices

give seminars

Consent

By selecting "I Agree" below, you acknowledge that you have read and understood the information provided to you by the researchers and consent to participate in this study.

 [Copy chart](#)

2 responses

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SUMMARY OF FINAL RESPONSES

Column 3 What factors most significantly influence your current eating habits?

- 1. I eat breakfast at 9am or 10am, lunch at 1pm or 2pm, dinner at 7pm or 8pm. I usually eat home-cooked meals. Academic Workload, particularly at the time
 - 2. For rice meal, 2, one for breakfast, one for lunch. Most of the times, I do not eat rice meal for dinner, Academic Workload, particularly at the time
 - 3. Home-cooked meals
-
- 1. I eat lunch around 12:30PM, dinner at 7PM. I usually eat home-cooked meals such as eggs and eggplant.
 - 2. I get snacks 2 times a day. It depends. Food accessibility
 - 3. Home-cooked meals such as eggs and eggplant
-
- 1. I eat breakfast at 6:30 AM, lunch at 12:30 PM, dinner at 7:30 PM.
 - 2. I usually eat 3 meals per day Food accessibility
 - 3. Home cooked meals and Fast food
-
- I normally eat lunch at around 1PM. I usually have 2 meals a day. Food accessibility
 - 1. I eat breakfast at 7:30 AM, lunch at 12:30 PM, dinner at 7:30 PM. Academic workload
-
- I mostly start eating at afternoon at 3pm and 2 meals a day. Food accessibility
 - I take my lunch usually around 12 noon. Dinner is a home-cooked meal. Academic workload
-
- I eat lunch at 11:50 am or 12:00pm, dinner at 8:00pm. Depends if am Academic workload
 - One meal a day then light snacks. 16:8 ratio. 12nn-1 Food accessibility

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FOLLOW-UP: Why do these factors affect your choice? How familiar are you with SSCR-Manila or CHED guidelines?

I really prefer home-cooked meals since I know how to cook.	1
Both financial constraints and food accessibility, cost.	2
I cook for myself since I lived in a dormitory.	1
The location of my dorm is surrounded by different food options.	1
because of many readings.	1
Cause that's all around here that have affordable prices.	2
Busy schedule.	1
Academic workload effects my eating choices because I have to eat fast.	3
I don't like to stock much food at home so I wouldn't.	1

FOLLOW-UP: If aware, how do these policies affect you? What challenges do you face in maintaining a balanced diet?

N/A	Time
I'm not entirely aware, but I'm cautious with everything I eat.	Budget, Time, Limited healthy options near campus.
not familiar	Budget, Time
not aware	Budget, Limited healthy options near campus
not aware	Budget, Time
Yes	Budget, Time, Lack of cooking facilities, Limited healthy options.
Not aware.	Time
Dormitory rules- because this rule in my dorm limits my choices.	Time, Lack of cooking facilities, Limited healthy options.
Unaware.	Time, Cultural/Dietary Preferences, Location

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How do these challenges affect your academic performance?
 FOLLOW-UP: How do you navigate these challenges?
 1. Focus during exams
 2. Energy levels
 3. Attendance

Time Management	Energy levels
I try to choose healthier food options as much as possible	2
I started allotting money and time to cook for myself	1. I don't have any experience wherein I lost my focus 2. Skipping meals affects my performance in school 3. It doesn't have any effect on my attendance
I try as much as possible to balance my consumption by setting a time schedule and budget for my daily	2
Budgeting and time plan	I'm fine
Ordering online.	It does not affect me much. I can still focus and have
Meal prep- only use for microwave meals only in my room Online ordering- This is my savior from the late dinner	Energy levels
I get necessary food after school on my way home.	It doesn't affect me.

FOLLOW-UP: Describe a specific instance where the relationship between your diet and mental clarity got affected. How do you perceive the relationship between your diet and mental clarity?

When I have a lot of workload, when what I eat isn't healthy, the relationship between diet and mental clarity gets affected.

It only affects my energy level. I can manage during exams. I don't really have any unhealthy stress eating.

I performed badly during exam whenever I don't have a balanced diet. I think my diet is pretty balanced and good for me.

None so far.	In my case, I don't think there's much of a relationship between diet and mental clarity because I don't eat breakfast my mind doesn't work.
None	Sometimes I do stress eating
No specific instance	Balanced
Lack of sleep	When I eat poorly or skip meals due to time.
None	Before, snacks is a temporary solution to stress. For

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Do certain foods make you feel more anxious or fat? Do you think improving your diet will help you manage your anxiety?

No	Yes
Yes	Yes
No	Yes
No	No
Yes	Yes
Maybe	Maybe
No	Yes
Maybe	Maybe
No	Yes

During busy periods (e.g., exams), how do you adjust your eating habits?
 1. Meal preparation
 Describe a time when poor nutrition (e.g., skipping meals) affected your performance.
 2. Ordering delivery
 3. Skipping meals
 4. Stress eating

When I skip meals, it feels like my brain isn't functioning properly. Ordering delivery

There's a time when I got acidic because I only had 1 & 2

skipping meals because I didn't have enough time to eat. This past few weeks I usually skip meals whenever I have exams.

None yet	4z
skipping meals makes my energy low specially in n	meal preparation
Makes me feel sleepy	Skipping meals
Relying on junk food.	2
Skipping food	Ordering meals
Pancit canton as a to-go meal affected my perform	I make time for meal preparation

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What personal strategies or resources help you manage stress? What small, sustainable changes have improved your health and well-being?

Self-discipline	As a student, I really like drinking water, and I don't
Online content (e.g. vlogs), Self-discipline	Eating more fruits and vegetable, healthier drinking
Self-discipline	drinking more water helps a lot
Peer support	drinking more water
Self-discipline	drinking more water
Self-discipline	Reducing alcoholic beverages and drinking more w
Self-discipline	Exercising.
Self-discipline	Drinking water, and eat healthy food
Online content (e.g. vlogs), Self-discipline	Hydrating more, no junk food, and meal timing.

How do you think SSCR-Manila or CHED could better support student health and well-being? By selecting 'I Agree' below, you acknowledge that you agree with the statement.

To provide more healthy meal and delicious options:	I Agree
By giving students a budget friendly meal but healthy:	I Agree
offer a better and affordable meals for students	I Agree
by organizing seminars related to this matter	I Agree
to make their student healthier	I Agree
Free food at canteen	I Agree
Hear the students out about schedule and blocking	I Agree
I don't have any idea about that	I Agree
Suggest better food and balanced meal in the cafe:	I Agree

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APPENDIX C: DEDUCTIVE CODEBOOK

Column 1	FOOD		Code	TIME		Code	BUDGE T
Links to			Links to			Links to	
Level	1		Level	1		Level	1
Short definition	An everyda y nourish ment that the Legal Manage ment Student s are taking.		Short definiti on	When they are eating.		Short definiti on	The financia l plan or allowan ce allocate d by Legal Manage ment student s for their food expens es.

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Full definition	<p>It refers to any substance consumed for the nourishment, energy, and sustenance that contributes to the overall well-being and functioning of Legal Management</p>		Full definition	<p>It refers to every instances when they are eating a breakfast, lunch, snacks and dinner.</p>		Full definition	<p>The budget refers to the amount of money that Legal Management student sets aside or have available for purchasing food, whether through personal funds,</p>
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student s. It include s meals, snacks, and beverag es that they consum e daily, whether prepare d at home, purchas ed from fast food chains, or obtaine d from universi							allowan ces, or other financia l means. This budget may be influenc ed by their persona l finance s, financia l aid, or the cost of living in dormito ries or nearby
--	--	--	--	--	--	--	---

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	ty canteen and conveni ence stores.						areas.
When to use	It is to be use when describi ng what the student s are eating daily (like the meals or snacks) while living in dormito		When to use	In the time-rel ated challen ges that prevent student s from making healthy food choices or habits.		When to use	This code should be used when describi ng the financia l aspects of the student s' food choices, such as how they

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	ries.						plan, allocate, or manage their spending on food during their time in school.
Example	The Legal Management students living in dormitories often rely on		Example	A lack of time because of the academic workload leads the Legal Manage		Example	Many Legal Management students living in dormitories are conscious of

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	fast food due to limited cooking facilities or time to cook themselves a proper and nutritious meals.			ment student s to choose fast food or convenience over home-cooked meals.			their budget and often choose affordable meal options like instant noodles or fast food to avoid overspending.
When not to use	In describing factors that are shaping		When not to use	As vague references. We will need to		When not to use	This code should not be used when

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	their eating behaviors.			be specific			discussing factors unrelated to financial constraints, such as personal preferences, eating habits, or social influences.
<i>Note:</i>							

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MEAL Code LOCATI ON			MEAL Code FREQUE NCY			FOOD Code PREFEREN CE	
Links to	Food Prefere nce		Links to	Academi c Workloa d		Links to	FOOD
Level	3		Level	4		Level	2

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Short definition	The location where students consume their meals.	Short definition	The number of meals Legal Management students consume daily.	Short definition	The types of food Legal Management students prefer to eat.
Full definition	Refers to where Legal Management students are consuming their meals, whether they	Full definition	Refers to how often Legal Management students consume meals throughout the day, including	Full definition	Refers to the specific types of food Legal Management students favor, such as fast food, home cooked meals, or

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	are eating in the dormitory, outside of dorms, fast food chains, or in university canteens and other communal spaces.			breakfast, lunch, and dinner. This can be categorized into frequent meals (3+ meals/day), moderate meals (2 meals/day), or skipping meals.			other healthy options. This could also involve preferences in diets like high protein, low carbs, vegan/vegetarian, or gluten-free.
When to use	When discussing		When to use	When discussing how		When to use	When discussing the food

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	where Legal Manag ement student s typicall y eat their meals.			often Legal Manage ment students are eating during the day.			preference s of LEgal Managem ent students, including healthy/un healthy eating habits and dietary restriction s.
Examp le	Student s usually have breakfa st in the dormito ry, but for		Examp le	Most Legal Manage ment students report having 3 meals a day, though		Examp le	Although most students enjoy fast food, a few prefer healthier options like salads or

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	lunch and dinner, they prefer eating at local fast food restaurants near the college.		some may skip breakfast due to having early morning classes.			vegetarian meals.
When not to use	When discussing what type of food they are eating.	When not to use	When talking about meal content, type, or meal preparation (ex.	When not to use		When discussing meal frequency or location.

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				self-cooked vs. purchased).			

TIME CONSTRAINTS			BUDGET CONSTRAINTS			ACADEMIC WORKLOAD	
Code			Code			Code	
Links to	Time		Links to	Budget & Meal Location		Links to	Time Constraints
Level	2		Level	2, 3		Level	3

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Short definition	Lack of time available to prepare meals or eat properly.	Short definition	Financial limitations affecting students' food choices.	Short definition	School tasks and responsibilities the Legal Management ent students need to comply with.
Full definition	Refers to how student s' busy schedules or academic commitments affect their	Full definition	Refers to how student s' budget for food may affect their eating choices, such as	Full definition	Refers to the total amount of academic tasks, responsibilities, and commitments like lectures, assignme

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ability to cook, prepare meals, or eat at regular times, leading to reliance on quick or convenient food options.			opting for cheaper fast food or skipping meals due to financial limitations.			nts, exams, and study hours that Legal Management ent students are required to complete daily, which may influence their eating habits.
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When to use	When discussing how Legal Management student s' schedules ex. class timings, study hours, impact their food consumption and eating habits.		When to use	When discussing financial constraints and how they impact student s' eating habits and food choices.		When to use	As a factor to healthy eating or meal preparation.
--------------------	--	--	--------------------	--	--	--------------------	--

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	Examp e	<p>With tight schedules, students often grab quick meals from the campus convenience store instead of preparing their own food in the dormitory.</p>	Examp e	<p>"Due to limited financial resources, some students choose cheaper fast food options rather than healthier, more expensive meals."</p>	Examp e	<p>Legal Management Students face time constraints due to academic workload, resulting for them to choose fast food or convenient foods over home-cooked meals.</p>
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When not to use	When discussing the specific food consumed or dietary restrictions.		When not to use	When discussing meal preferences or the quality of food consumed.		When not to use	When discussing meal preferences or the quality of food consumed.

APPENDIX D: INDUCTIVE CODEBOOK

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Column 1	PURPOSE	CODE	PARTICIPANT /
What are the daily eating routines of students in t	Details daily rou	Daily Routine	"I eat breakfast
What key factors (e.g., financial constraints, dorm	Identifies key ini	Influencing Fact	"Academic Worl
To what extent are students aware of SSCR-Manil	Awareness of th	Students' Aware	"1"
What challenges do students face in maintaining	Identifies challe	Challenges	"Time"
How do dietary challenges and poor nutritional ha	Identifies nutriti	Performance Ef	"When I skip me
What is the perceived relationship between diet, s	Understands th	Diet & Mental H	"The relationshi
How do students adjust their eating habits during	Determine stud	Eating Adjustm	"Ordering delive
What personal strategies and small, sustainable c	Identify student	Personal Chang	"Self-discipline,
What improvements do students suggest for SSC	Recognize solut	Suggested Solu	"To provide mor

PARTICIPANT E	PARTICIPANT C	PARTICIPANT I	PARTICIPANT E	PARTICIPANT F	PARTICIPANT C
"I eat lunch aro	"I eat breakfast	"I normally eat l	1	"I mostly start e	"I take my lunch
"Both financial c	"Food accessibi	"Food accessibi	"Academic worl	"Food accessibi	"Academic worl
"2", "I'm not enti	"1"	"1"	"1"	"2"	"1"
"Budget", "Time	"skipping meals	"Budget, Limite	"Budget, Time"	"Budget, Time, l	"Time"
"There's a time	"Skipping meals	"Energy Levels"	"skipping meals	"Makes me feel	
	"I think my diet	"No relationship	"By exercising b	"Sometimes I d	"Balanced"
"1 & 2"	"This past few v	"4z"	"meal preparati	"Skipping meal:	"2"
"Online content	"Self-discipline,	"Peer support",	"Self-discipline",	"Self-discipline"	"Self-discipline"
"By giving stude	"offer a better a	"by organizing s	"to make their s	"Free food at ca	"Hear the stude

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PARTICIPANT 1	PARTICIPANT 1
"I eat lunch at 1	"One meal a day
"Academic work	"Food accessibi
"3" "Dormitory n	"1"
"Time, Lack of c	"Time, Cultural/
"Energy Levels"	"Pancit canton e
"When I eat poc	Before, snacks
"Ordering meals	"I make time for
"Self-discipline"	"Online content
	"Suggest better

RESEARCH QUI	PURPOSE	CODE	SUB-CODE	PARTICIPANT /	PARTICIPANT E
What are the da		Daily Routine			
What key factor		Influencing Fact	Time & Budget	"When I have a	"It only affects r
To what extent :		Students' Aware			
What challenge		The challenges	Stressful Times	"The relationshi	
How do dietary		Performance Ef	Tiredness & Fox		
What is the perc		Diet & Mental	Stress Eating		"I don't really ha
How do student		Eating Adjustm	Covenience	" Preparing/Ord	"Ordering delive
What personal :		Personal Chang	Self-Discipline	"Self-discipline	"Self-discipline"
What improvem		Suggested Solu	Better & Cheap	"To provide moi	"By giving stude

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PARTICIPANT C PARTICIPANT D PARTICIPANT E PARTICIPANT F PARTICIPANT G PARTICIPANT H

"I started allotin "I try as much a "because of ma "Busy schedule. "Academic worl
 "because i dont "Lack of sleep"
 "I performed ba
 "Sometimes I di
 "This past few v "meal preparati "Skipping meal: "Ordering meals
 "Self-discipline", "drinking more \ "Self-discipline", "Self-discipline" "Self-discipline" "Self-discipline"
 "offer a better a "Free food at ca

PARTICIPANT I

"Before, snacks
 "I make time for
 "Self-discipline",
 "Suggest better